

Cultural Integration in Mergers and Acquisitions: Impact on Financial and Deal Dynamics

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Abstract

We examine the influence of corporate culture on M&A outcomes by analyzing text data from 10-K filings using the culture dictionary developed by Li et al. (2021) and employing Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques. Individual cultural dimensions—innovation, integrity, quality, respect, and teamwork — affect various M&A metrics. Specifically, respect enhances cumulative abnormal returns for both acquiring and target firms, while innovation and quality improve the long-term financial performance of acquiring firms, boosting profitability and valuation. Integrity within the target firm and quality within the acquired firm's culture positively influence deal premiums. Robust cultural values, including innovation, integrity, and quality, facilitate quicker deal completions. Interestingly, teamwork exhibits no significant impact on M&A outcomes. This research underscores the strategic importance of cultural alignment in M&A and is supported by case studies that illustrate these findings and their practical implications.

Keywords: Mergers and acquisitions, firm performance, natural language processing, corporate culture

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1. INTRODUCTION

In today's global business environment, mergers and acquisitions (M&A) are vital strategies for growth, market expansion, and gaining competitive advantage. While strategic synergies and financial metrics have traditionally been the focus, the role of corporate culture in M&A success is increasingly recognized (Healy et al., 1992; Clark and Ofek, 1994; Seth et al., 2002; Cui and Leung, 2020). Cultural integration, encompassing shared values, norms, and behaviors, can significantly influence the success or failure of M&A transactions (Schein, 1988; O'Reilly and Chatman, 1996; Streicher et al., 2018; Graham et al., 2022). Market perceptions often view greater cultural differences negatively, anticipating integration challenges (Hertel et al., 2024). We address a gap in the literature by analyzing unstructured data from 10-K filings and using the culture dictionary by Li et al. (2021) to assess cultural dimensions such as quality, teamwork, integrity, innovation, and respect. This approach provides a detailed analysis of how cultural factors influence key M&A outcomes, including announcement returns, deal premiums, completion speed, and long-term performance.

We show several key findings: First, the cultural attributes of acquiring firms significantly affect market reactions to M&A announcements, with traits such as respect and integrity associated with higher cumulative abnormal returns (CAR). For target firms, a culture of respect leads to notably positive market reactions, highlighting their role in enhancing market perception during M&A events. Respect emerges as a crucial factor in enhancing market perception during M&A events.

Additionally, we show that cultural dimensions like innovation and quality are crucial for the long-term performance of acquiring firms. Firms excelling in these areas demonstrate better valuation and financial health, indicating that a strong culture of innovation and quality supports sustained success in post-M&A. We further show that target firms with a robust culture of integrity command higher deal premiums, as acquirers value integrity for their role in facilitating smooth integration and enhancing post-merger value creation. Acquiring firms with a robust culture of quality have higher deal premiums. Moreover, firms with strong cultural values in innovation and quality tend to complete deals more swiftly, minimizing transaction

costs and uncertainties. A strong corporate culture fosters trust and efficiency in negotiations and integration, thereby streamlining the M&A process.

This paper makes a significant contribution to the literature by exploring the largely overlooked intersection of corporate culture and M&A outcomes. It offers a comprehensive analysis of how corporate culture shapes various aspects of M&A transactions, providing fresh insights into deal premiums, completion speed, and long-term performance. By integrating insights from organizational behavior and institutional theory, this study extends the foundational theories of corporate culture and M&A performance. Traditional finance theories, including agency theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976) and the resource-based view (Barney, 1991), predominantly emphasize the economic and strategic dimensions of M&As, often downplaying the critical role of corporate culture. However, we show that cultural dimensions—such as respect, innovation, and integrity—are not peripheral but central drivers of M&A success.

Incorporating institutional theory, which highlights the influence of normative and cognitive frameworks within organizations (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983), we show how deeply embedded cultural traits impact post-merger integration and long-term financial outcomes. Additionally, we introduce a behavioral perspective, suggesting that cultural alignment is crucial for effective human capital integration, which is essential for realizing synergies (Weber & Camerer, 2003). This interdisciplinary approach addresses existing gaps in the literature and provides a holistic view of M&A dynamics, asserting that the integration of cultures is as vital as the alignment of strategic goals. Lastly, real-world case studies are presented to reinforce the empirical findings and illustrate their practical implications.

Assessing corporate culture presents notable challenges, as it often depends on resource-intensive methods like comprehensive employee interviews, which can be costly and impractical for pre-acquisition evaluations. Furthermore, post-merger interviews may introduce biases. To circumvent these limitations, various proxies are used, including company rankings, corporate social responsibility policies, CEO demographics, language, and luxury preferences. However, some proxies, like World Value Survey data and Hofstede's indices, are available only at the national level, while others, such as MSCI's (formerly KLD) metrics, are restricted to large public firms, complicating cultural analysis for smaller entities. We transcend these limitations by employing a mixed-method approach that combines qualitative analysis of unstructured text data from 10-K filings with quantitative analysis of structured financial data

from Compustat and CRSP databases. By employing Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques to analyze unstructured text data from 10-K filings, this paper provides new insights into the role of corporate culture¹. NLP techniques, such as sentiment analysis, have been increasingly applied to financial analysis and document examinations, revealing insights into organizational behavior and market perceptions (Lee et al., 2010; Nassirtoussi et al., 2014).

While we offer valuable contributions, we acknowledge limitations such as data constraints and potential biases inherent in textual analysis. These limitations highlight the need for further research to deepen the understanding of corporate culture's impact on M&A success.

2. Literature Review

Mergers and acquisitions (M&As) are extensively studied in finance, focusing on their impact on stock prices, shareholder value, and long-term performance. M&A serves as a strategic tool for enhancing competitive advantage and comes in various forms: vertical mergers streamline supply chains; horizontal mergers consolidate market power; conglomerate mergers diversify; asset acquisitions target specific assets; and stock acquisitions involve buying shares. While M&As can boost market share, achieve economies of scale, and reduce costs, they also pose risks such as potential shareholder value loss, management challenges, and overestimated synergies (Roll, 1986; Ross et al., 2009; Ma et al., 2011).

Hertel et al. (2023) examine acquirer-target cultural differences in U.S. domestic M&A deals using employee reviews, finding that greater cultural similarity is associated with improved deal outcomes and smoother integration. Brede et al. (2024) analyze the influence of organizational cultural differences during both the transaction and post-merger integration phases, showing that early cultural alignment significantly reduces integration risk and enhances synergy realization. Fantaguzzi and Handscomb (2024) highlight that cultural compatibility boosts post-deal financial performance and stakeholder satisfaction. Scantlebury (2024) explores the dynamic relationship between culture and M&A activity, revealing that firms prioritizing cultural due diligence experience fewer post-merger disruptions and greater long-term value creation.

³ Natural Language Processing (NLP), a subset of artificial intelligence (AI), merges computational linguistics with machine learning and deep learning to process and analyze extensive natural language data. NLP drives applications like sentiment analysis and text summarization. In sentiment analysis, NLP deciphers unstructured text to extract nuanced sentiments, with machine learning models or rule-based systems classifying and assigning granular sentiment scores.

The outcomes of M&As encompass operating and financial performance, market share, competitive positioning, operational efficiency, and employee dynamics. Prior research has used methods like event studies (Sudarsanam and Mahate, 2003) and accounting-based measures (Hoskisson et al., 1994; Zollo and Singh, 2004) to assess M&A impacts. Event studies analyze short-term security price changes to gauge economic effects but may require extended periods for complete assessment (Mackinlay, 1997; Gopaldaswamy et al., 2008). Baker et al. (2012) find that acquiring firms' long-term operating performance drops with past superior performance.

Barber and Lyon (1996) evaluate long-term performance by comparing M&A firms with industry peers or non-acquired firms, using benchmarking. This method provides direct economic impact insights but can be limited by variability in accounting practices (McWilliams and Siegel, 1997). Factors influencing M&A success include strategic fitness, due diligence, business synergies, and management capabilities (Harding and Yale, 2002; Delis et al., 2021). King et al. (2004) highlight conglomerate status, acquisition experience, acquisition type, and payment method as key determinants. Lynch and Lind (2002) identify pre- and post-merger factors leading to failure, including inadequate due diligence and integration challenges. Gadiesh and Ormiston (2002) point to inadequate strategic rationale, overpayment, and integration issues as factors of failure, while overpayment remains a critical consideration (Morck et al., 1989; Sirower, 1996; Hayward and Hambrick, 1997).

Integration, a critical phase involving the alignment of organizational structures and cultures, significantly affects M&A performance (Haspeslagh and Jemison, 1993; Larsson and Lubatkin, 2001). Capron (1999) and Karim (2006) stress that effective integration converts strategic vision into tangible results, impacting acquisition success. Delis et al. (2021) show that management practices are crucial for M&A success, enhancing predictive models of abnormal returns. They offer a robust metric for evaluating management practices across various conditions.

The influence of corporate culture on M&A outcomes has gained attention. While traditional research has focused on cultural compatibility, recent studies explore how the culture of the acquiring firm affects M&A success. Cultural mismatches, such as differences in managerial style and employee adaptability, are cited as major failure factors (Nahavandi and Malekzadeh, 1988; Lynch and Lind, 2002). Definitions of corporate culture vary, with scholars emphasizing shared values, norms, and behavior (Schein, 1988; O'Reilly and Chatman, 1996;

Ortega-Parra and Sastre-Castillo, 2013; Graham et al., 2022). Research methods for assessing corporate culture include surveys, interviews, and text analysis. Li et al. (2021) use machine learning to evaluate cultural values from earnings calls, linking culture to business performance. Graham et al. (2022) survey executives to explore culture's impact on value creation and ethical choices. Guiso et al. (2015) analyze company values and employee perceptions to assess integrity and performance. Other studies, such as Gorondutse and Hilman (2019) and Lasrado and Kassem (2020), show positive correlations between culture and performance, while Lim (1995) critiques these claims, highlighting methodological and performance measurement issues. Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic has profoundly affected market conditions, introducing heightened volatility and information asymmetry that have reshaped the strategic motivations and execution of M&A transactions (Piccotti & Saba, 2024; Tampakoudis et al., 2021; Deckert, 2021).

3. Hypothesis Development

3.1 Corporate Culture and Short-Term M&A Announcement Returns

By examining how M&A news is absorbed into stock prices, we aim to assess market efficiency, investor sentiment, and expectations of merger synergies and risks following Doukas and Zhang (2021). Prior research highlights diverse factors affecting market volatility, such as weather, inflation, and geopolitical events (Hirshleifer and Shumway, 2003; Sathyanarayana and Gargesa, 2018; Yousaf et al., 2022). Studies on M&A impacts reveal conflicting results, with some indicating negative returns for acquiring firms and positive returns for targets (Campa & Hernando, 2004; Seth et al., 2002; Drymbetas and Kyriazopoulos, 2014, Baker et al., 2021), while Wong and Cheung (2009) suggest opposite effects. We hypothesize that acquiring firms experience negative cumulative abnormal returns, while target firms have positive returns. Additionally, it posits that corporate culture significantly affects short-term stock returns around M&A announcements.

H1: *Acquiring firms have negative cumulative abnormal returns during M&A announcements.*

H2: *Target firms experience positive cumulative abnormal returns during M&A announcements.*

H3: *Corporate culture significantly impacts short-term stock returns for acquiring and target firms during M&A announcements.*

3.2 Corporate Culture and M&A Long-Term Financial Performance

We evaluate how corporate culture impacts the long-term performance of acquiring firms post-M&A. We examine whether mergers and acquisitions fulfill strategic goals and assess financial stability, including profitability and solvency. We contrast short-term announcement returns with long-term outcomes, as longer periods allow merger effects to fully manifest (Agrawal and Jaffe, 2001; Rosen, 2006).

While significant research addresses short-term performance, the long-term effects of M&As are less explored. Studies yield mixed results on long-term performance: some indicate negative impacts (Agrawal et al., 2019), while others suggest positive effects (Ito, 1991; Bhaumik and Selarka, 2012; Zhang et al., 2018). Factors like ownership concentration and managerial ability have been linked to performance variations (Bhaumik and Selarka, 2012; Cui and Leung, 2020). We propose that firms with cultures emphasizing innovation, quality, integrity, teamwork, and respect are expected to achieve superior long-term financial outcomes.

H4: *Corporate culture positively impacts the long-term financial performance of acquiring firms.*

3.3 Corporate Culture and M&A Deal Premium

M&A success depends on future profit expectations and the acquisition cost relative to those expectations. The premium, defined as the bid price exceeding the target's market value, significantly influences shareholder returns for acquiring and target firms (Sirower, 1962; Hayward and Hambrick, 1997; Grullon et al., 1997; Moeller et al., 2004; Moeller et al., 2005).

Research shows mixed effects of premiums on shareholder returns. Higher premiums could signal potential synergies, leading to positive returns (Bradley et al., 1988; Antoniou et al., 2007), or they could indicate overpayment, resulting in negative returns (Sirower, 1962; Varaiya and Ferris, 1987; Schwert, 2002). Some studies suggest that these effects may be balanced, showing no significant overall relationship (Bharadwaj and Shivdasani, 2003; Cheng and Leung, 2004; Moeller et al., 2005).

Additional research highlights various factors influencing deal premiums. For instance, Ozdemir et al. (2021) find a positive link between a target firm's CSR performance and deal

premiums, particularly in service industries. Skaife and Wangerin (2011) report that low-quality financial reporting correlates with higher premiums. Perafan et al. (2022) observe that acquirers offer higher premiums in inter-industry deals when targets engage in earnings management. Chamberlain and Fabre (2016) note that management control strength affects premiums, while Viale et al. (2016) find that target valuation complexity increases premiums. Chow et al. (2016) show that targets avoiding tax shelters receive higher premiums, and Wu and Chiang (2019) find that innovative firms with high R&D spending are more likely to receive higher premiums. We propose that corporate culture positively impacts deal premiums.

H5: Corporate culture is positively and significantly related to deal premiums.

3.4 Corporate Culture and M&A Deal Completion Speed

Research on the speed of M&A deal completion is sparse, but the literature on Post-Merger Integration (PMI) has shed light on the importance of integration speed. Gerpott (1995) find that centralizing R&D during PMI positively affects integration speed. Rosenzweig (1993) argue that the integration approach, including speed, should balance strategic interdependence with organizational autonomy. Bragado (1992) suggests that slower integration could be beneficial, particularly when firms have differing cultures. While literature emphasizes the role of relatedness in integration speed, it lacks extensive empirical validation. Inkpen et al. (2000) underscore that rapid integration is crucial for technology firms, whereas Olie (1994) and Ranft and Lord (2002) advocate for gradual integration to reduce conflicts and build trust.

Most research mainly focuses on the duration between M&A announcement and completion. Bereskin et al. (2018) find that mergers between firms with similar CSR traits are 18.2% faster. Hwang and Roh (2015) demonstrate that firms with prior acquisition experience reduce deal completion time. Cardillo and Harasheh (2022) reveal that greater ESG rating disparities between acquirers and targets lead to longer deal timings. We aim to address the gap in understanding the impact of corporate culture on M&A deal completion speed and propose the following hypothesis:

H6: Corporate culture is inversely related to M&A deal completion speed.

4. Data and Methodology

Data on U.S. mergers and acquisitions from 2010 to 2020 is sourced from the Thompson SDC database. The dataset includes deals with a minimum value of USD 5 billion, where the acquirer's post-merger ownership is between 50% and 100%, and the acquirer's pre-announcement stake is between 0% and 50%. Only transactions involving publicly listed companies are considered, excluding techniques such as spin-offs, recapitalizations, self-tenders, and minority stakes. The final dataset comprises 1,456 deals, emphasizing large corporations and ensuring relevance. The selection criteria also ensured that target companies were at least 10% the size of the acquirers, following methods outlined by Schneider et al. (2022), Cihan and Tice (2014), and Moeller et al. (2004).

To ensure the significance of transactions, only those where the acquired firms are at least 10% of the size of the acquirers are included. The relative size is calculated by dividing the deal value by the acquirer market capitalization, using methodologies from Schneider et al. (2022), Cihan and Tice (2014), and Moeller et al. (2004). This filtering based on relative size criteria yielded a final dataset of 813 companies for analysis. M&A values are sourced from the SDC database, while market capitalization data comes from the Compustat database.² To measure corporate culture, We extract the "Business" (Item 1) and "Management's Discussion and Analysis" (Item 7) sections from the 10-K filings of 813 M&A deals using the SEC database. A machine-learning script with an SEC API is employed to retrieve filings from the five years preceding each M&A announcement. Due to incomplete filings, the final dataset included 534 acquirers and 571 targets.

We investigate how corporate culture influences the long-term financial performance and short-term announcement returns of acquiring firms, as well as how it affects the M&A deal premium and completion time for target firms. Control variables include M&A deal characteristics (within-state, within-industry) and firm-specific attributes (Book-to-market ratio, ROA, leverage, sales growth). Leverage is the book value of debt divided by the sum of equity market value and the book value of debt; Book-to-market ratio (BM_ratio) is the ratio of book value to the market value of equity; and sales growth is computed as: $(sales_t - sales_{t-1}) / (sales_{t-1})$, where t depicts the year, as per Li (2011).

⁴ Due to some firms' unavailability of Compustat data, the dataset was initially reduced from 1,456 to 1,196 companies. Further filtering to meet the 10% relative size criterion resulted in a final dataset of 800 companies.

4.1 Methodology and Model Specification

4.1.1 Corporate Culture

Text data for acquiring and the target firms in the final sample is sourced from the SEC database. The text is then normalized to ensure consistency and eliminate language variations. After generating unigram and bigram text representations, the cultural dictionary developed by Li et al. (2021) and the term frequency (TF) scoring is applied to assess five cultural values: teamwork, quality, integrity, innovation, and respect. Li et al. (2021) used a word embedding model, a semi-supervised machine learning approach, to analyze 209,480 earnings call transcripts and study corporate culture. This model helps to understand the meanings of words and phrases, creating unigrams and bigrams of corporate culture words. TF scoring determines the frequency of each cultural value term in the 10-K filings. TF is defined as:

$$TF(t, d) = \frac{\text{Number of times term } t \text{ appears in document } d}{\text{Total number of terms in document } d}$$

The term frequency increases with the number of occurrences in the filing (Li et al., 2021; Loughran & McDonald, 2011).

4.1.2 Short-Term Announcement Returns

To assess the influence of corporate culture on short-term announcement returns, this study employs robust regressions to estimate the abnormal returns of acquirers and targets using an event study methodology. The regression model examines the cumulative abnormal returns (CAR(-2,2)) for both acquiring and target firms, concerning both individual and composite dimensions of corporate culture. These dependent variables, representing the cumulative abnormal returns over the event window, are derived using an event study methodology as outlined by Keown and Pinkerton (1981), Ito (1991), and Mackinlay (1997).

The event study methodology, a prevalent framework for assessing the impact of events like M&A announcements on stock returns, entails defining an event window to estimate abnormal returns. In this analysis, the event window spans from two days before two days following the M&A announcement, with the announcement day (time 0) expected to significantly influence stock prices. Moreover, a 252-trading-day window, extending up to 20

trading days before the announcement, is designated as the estimation window to reflect standard market conditions, isolated from the anticipatory effects of the announcement. This estimation window selection follows the methodology of Andriosopoulos et al. (2016). The market model below is employed to derive the cumulative average abnormal return (CAR):

$$R_{it} = \alpha + \beta \cdot R_{mt} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

In this model, R_{it} represents the return of stocks i at time t , R_{mt} is the market return at time t , ε_{it} is the error term, and parameters α and β are derived from regressing the stock's returns against market returns during the estimation window. Abnormal returns are calculated after determining the expected returns. According to Mackinlay (1997), the distribution of abnormal returns is $AR_{it} \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$. The expected return is:

$$E(R_{it}) = E(\alpha) + \beta \cdot E(R_{mt})$$

$E(R_{it})$ is the expected return of stock i at time t . The abnormal returns are calculated as:

$$AR_{it} = R_{it} - E(R_{it})$$

To determine the impact of corporate culture on short-term announcement returns (STR) for acquiring and target firms, where the event window spans from two days before to two days (CAR(-2,2)), the following models are utilized:

$$STR_Acquirer = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Culture Dimension})_{it} + \beta_i \text{ Controls}_{it} + \zeta + \lambda + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$STR_Target = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Culture Dimension})_{it} + \beta_i \text{ Controls}_{i,t} + \zeta + \lambda + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

Here, ζ denotes firm-fixed effects and λ indicates year-fixed effects. The individual and composite cultural dimensions are used as independent variables separately in Equations 1 and 2. The composite culture scores are represented by “*zculture*”, the z-score of the sum of five cultural values, and “*cultureD*”, a dummy variable set to one if a firm's cultural value sum exceeds the sample median, and zero otherwise. Both *zculture* and *cultureD* are employed as independent variables separately in the regression analysis. The individual cultural dimensions—comprising scores for innovation, integrity, quality, respect, and teamwork—are also analyzed independently. The model also incorporates firm-level controls, including the BM_ratio, leverage, ROA, and sales growth, alongside deal-specific variables. Industry and year-fixed effects are accounted for to ensure robustness in the analysis.

4.1.3 Long-Term Financial Performance

This research explores how both individual and composite dimensions of corporate culture impact the post-acquisition financial performance of acquiring firms. Adopting the framework of Cui and Leung (2020), the study employs dependent variables to evaluate long-term performance over three years following the acquisition. These variables include $\Delta profitability$ indicating net profit margin, $\Delta valuation$ measured by the acquirers’ buy-and-hold abnormal returns (BHAR), and $\Delta solvency$ indicating interest coverage. The following regression models are employed to investigate this relationship:

$$\Delta valuation_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Culture Dimension})_{it} + \beta_i \text{Controls}_{it} + \zeta + \lambda + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta profit_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Culture Dimension})_{it} + \beta_i \text{Controls}_{it} + \zeta + \lambda + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta solvency_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Culture Dimension})_{it} + \beta_i \text{Controls}_{it} + \zeta + \lambda + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (5)$$

The composite scores *zculture* and *cultureD* and the individual cultural dimensions—comprising scores for innovation, integrity, quality, respect, and teamwork—are examined separately in distinct regression analyses. Building on Li et al. (2021), this study includes firm-level controls for acquirers: BM_ratio, leverage, ROA, and sales growth. Deal-specific variables, such as within-state and within-industry indicators, are considered. Collectively

termed "Controls" in equations 1 through 5, these variables are complemented by industry and year-fixed effects to account for market trends and temporal variations.

4.1.4 Deal Premium

The study explores the impact of both individual and composite cultural dimensions of acquiring and target firms on M&A deal premiums. The analysis centers on the deal premium variable, denoted as DP. This measure, based on methodologies from Boone and Mulherin (2008), Barger et al. (2008), and Skaife and Wangerin (2011) is calculated as the ratio of the target firm's offer price to its share price four weeks prior to the announcement, minus one. This standardized metric aims to illuminate how the target firm's corporate culture influences the financial terms of M&A transactions, specifically the premium paid by the acquiring firms.

$$DP_Target_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(Culture\ Dimension)_{it} + \beta_i Controls_{it} + \zeta + \lambda + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (6)$$

$$DP_Acquirer_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(Culture\ Dimension)_{it} + \beta_i Controls_{it} + \zeta + \lambda + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (7)$$

$$DP_Combined_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(zculture)_{it} + \beta_2(zculture_{Target} \times zculture_{Acquirer})_{it} + \beta_i Controls_{it} + \zeta + \lambda + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (8)$$

Equation 6 evaluates the effect of target firms' cultural traits on deal premiums, with the dependent variable being the deal premium and the independent variables comprising both individual and composite cultural dimensions (*cultureD*) of the target firms. Equation 7 investigates how the culture of acquiring firms, assessed through their composite score (*cultureD*) and individual cultural dimensions, impacts the deal premium. Equation 8 analyzes the influence of the composite cultural scores (*zculture*) of both target and acquiring firms, including the interaction between their cultural traits, on the deal premium, using distinct models. The combined culture score is constructed following Hasan (2022).

4.1.5 Deal Completion Speed

This study investigates whether "days to closing"—the interval between the M&A announcement and deal finalization—is affected by both individual and aggregate cultural measures of the target and acquiring firms. The "days to closing" (*DtoC*) variable, derived from

methodologies in Bereskin et al. (2018) and Cardillo and Harasheh (2022), measures the duration from announcement to completion. The analysis seeks to elucidate how corporate culture influences M&A execution efficiency, utilizing the following models:

$$Dtc_Target_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(Culture\ Dimension)_{it} + \beta_i Controls_{it} + \zeta + \lambda + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (9)$$

$$Dtc_Acquirer_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(Culture\ Dimension)_{it} + \beta_i Controls_{it} + \zeta + \lambda + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (10)$$

$$Dtc_Combined_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(zculture)_{it} + \beta_2(zculture_{target} \times zculture_{Acquirer})_{it} + \beta_i Controls_{it} + \zeta + \lambda + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (11)$$

Equation 9 analyzes how target firms' cultural traits influence deal completion speed, with "Dtc" as the dependent variable and the target firms' individual and composite score (*cultureD*) cultural dimensions as independent variables in distinct models. Equation 10 analyzes how acquiring firms' culture affects completion speed, using the acquiring firms' individual and composite score (*cultureD*) cultural dimensions separately. Equation 11 delves into the joint effects of the composite cultural scores (*zculture*) of both target and acquiring firms, as well as the interaction between their cultural traits, on the speed of deal completion. The analysis incorporates firm-level controls, industry, and year-fixed effects to ensure robustness.

5. Empirical Findings

5.1. Descriptive Statistics

5.1.1 Acquiring Firms

Table 1 summarizes acquiring firms' characteristics and performance from 2010 to 2020, detailing central tendencies and distributions for key metrics. It includes cultural dimensions and firm controls such as BM_ratio, ROA, leverage, sales growth, and within-state and within-industry indicators. The data, analyzed over a three-year post-acquisition period, features sample size, mean, standard deviation, quartiles, and range. The five-day cumulative abnormal returns (CAR(-2,2)) assess market reactions to acquisition announcements, with an average

CAR of 0.004 indicating a cautious market response and a range from -0.330 to 0.385 reflecting varied investor expectations of deal value creation.

Profitability, averaging 0.15 with a median of 0.057, shows modest gains for most of the firms post-acquisition, ranging from -3.266 to 5.62. With an average of -0.157, solvency indicates challenges in debt management, ranging from -656.875 to 474.187. Valuation, reflecting long-term returns, averages 67.807 and a median of 53.928, but spans from -99.799 to 726.498, showing significant variability in shareholder value. Cultural dimensions—Integrity, Respect, Innovation, Quality, and Teamwork—exhibit consistent scores, indicating stable cultural attributes with slight variations. The BM_ratio averages 0.474, suggesting moderate undervaluation. Sales growth averages 18.897%, ranging from -44.613% to 172.367%, reflecting diverse impacts on sales. Within-state and within-industry metrics show a strategic preference for industry alignment, with 22.6% of transactions within the same state and 66.9% within the same industry, on average.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of variables for acquiring firms.

This table summarizes the variables used to analyze acquiring firms from 2010 to 2020. The dependent variables are STR (CAR (-2,2)) which is the five-day cumulative abnormal return), Δ profitability (net profit margin performance within a three-year post-acquisition window), Δ solvency (interest coverage performance within a three-year post-acquisition window), and Δ valuation (buy-and-hold acquirers' returns within a three-year post-acquisition window). Independent variables include the five cultural dimensions: Innovation, Integrity, Quality, Respect, and Teamwork Scores. Control variables for acquirers are the BM_ratio, leverage, return on assets (ROA), and sales growth. M&A control variables are WithinState (dummy variable indicating if the acquirer and target are headquartered in the same state) and WithinIndustry (dummy variable indicating if the acquirer and target are in the same industry).

Variables	Count	Mean	Std. dev	Minimum	25%	Median	75%	Maximum
STR	489	0.004	0.084	-0.330	-0.026	0.006	0.036	0.385
Δ profitability	483	0.132	0.566	-3.266	-0.044	0.057	0.257	5.602
Δ solvency	532	-0.157	45.670	-656.875	-1.998	-0.010	1.501	474.187
Δ valuation	330	67.807	107.564	-99.806	0.929	53.928	112.517	726.498

RespectScore	489	0.0189	0.0126	0.0108	0.0148	0.0176	0.0219	0.0391
InnovationScore	489	0.0199	0.0139	0.0097	0.0151	0.0191	0.0233	0.0557
QualityScore	489	0.0198	0.0136	0.0096	0.0152	0.0188	0.0229	0.0522
TeamworkScore	489	0.0119	0.0089	0.0083	0.0105	0.0115	0.0127	0.0211
IntegrityScore	489	0.0161	0.0096	0.0093	0.0143	0.0158	0.0175	0.0261
BM_ratio	489	0.474	0.327	0.047	0.262	0.413	0.588	1.702
ROA	489	0.131	0.111	-0.460	0.106	0.138	0.177	0.359
Leverage	489	0.589	0.194	0.121	0.459	0.582	0.698	1.123
SalesGrowth	489	18.897	33.777	-44.613	1.897	10.427	28.727	172.362
WithinState	489	0.226	0.421	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	1.002
WithinIndustry	489	0.669	0.481	0.002	0.002	1.002	1.002	1.002

5.1.2. Target Firms

Table 2 presents the characteristics of target firms in M&A transactions from 2010 to 2020. Key metrics include the time to close deals, deal premiums, and various cultural scores. The average deal completion time was around 129 days, with a median of 106 days, showing considerable variability. Deal premiums averaged 0.008, with a wide range and significant variance in pricing. The mean CAR(-2,2) was 11.66%, though reactions varied from -45.43% to 136.66%. The "zculture" variable, representing the z-score of aggregate cultural values, ranges from -1.97 to 3.65, with a median of -0.105. Individual cultural dimensions show diverse scores: Integrity (mean 0.017), Respect (mean 0.019), Innovation (mean 0.022), Quality (mean 0.019), and Teamwork (mean 0.013). The BM_ratio averaged 0.521, ROA averaged 0.032, and leverage averaged 0.537, reflecting varied financial strategies. Within-state M&A occurs in 24.44% of cases, while within-industry M&A is more common at 65.5%.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of variables for target firms.

This table summarizes the variables used to analyze target firms from 2010 to 2020. The dependent variables are days to closing or DtoC (time between announcement and deal completion), deal premium (offered price to share price ratio four weeks before the announcement), and STR (CAR (-2,2) which is the five-day cumulative abnormal return). The primary independent variable is the z-score of the sum of a firm's five cultural values (zculture) from Li et al. (2021). Additionally, a dummy variable (cultureD) is introduced, indicating a value of 1 if a firm's cultural values exceed the sample median and 0 otherwise. zculture is

divided into Innovation, Integrity, Quality, Respect, and Teamwork Scores. Control variables include the *BM_ratio*, leverage, return on assets (ROA), *WithinState* (dummy for acquirer and target headquartered in the same state), and *WithinIndustry* (dummy for acquirer and target in the same industry).

Variables	Coun t	Mean	Std. dev	Minimu m	25%	Media n	75%	Maximu m
Days to Closing (<i>DtoC</i>)	514	129.7	112.141	8.013	62.00	106.00	162.02	742.033
<i>z(DealPremium)</i>	568	0.008	1.008	-0.561	-0.037	-0.323	0.036	8.497
<i>STR</i>	116	0.119	0.3045	-0.4543	0.016	0.0448	0.2848	1.3661
<i>zculture</i>	514	0.008	1.008	-1.977	-0.751	-0.105	0.576	3.650
<i>CultureD</i>	514	0.532	0.508	0.008	0.008	1.008	1.008	1.008
<i>IntegrityScore</i>	514	0.017	0.011	0.012	0.015	0.017	0.019	0.030
<i>RespectScore</i>	514	0.019	0.014	0.011	0.015	0.017	0.022	0.042
<i>InnovationScore</i>	514	0.022	0.015	0.011	0.016	0.020	0.027	0.044
<i>QualityScore</i>	514	0.020	0.015	0.011	0.016	0.020	0.026	0.043
<i>TeamworkScore</i>	514	0.013	0.010	0.010	0.011	0.012	0.014	0.023
<i>BM_ratio</i>	514	0.521	0.421	0.041	0.234	0.434	0.664	2.334
<i>ROA</i>	514	0.032	0.238	-1.002	-0.009	0.099	0.151	0.431
<i>Leverage</i>	514	0.537	0.275	0.064	0.329	0.521	0.710	1.353
<i>WithinState</i>	514	0.244	0.434	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	1.003
<i>WithinIndustry</i>	514	0.655	0.486	0.003	0.003	1.003	1.003	1.003

5.2 Empirical Results

5.2.1. Short-Term Announcement Returns

The model analysis investigates how corporate culture affects the five-day cumulative abnormal returns ($CAR(-2,2)$) for acquiring and the target firms, depicted as *STR_Acquirer* and *STR_Target*. Table 3 presents coefficients for acquiring firms. The composite culture score (*zculture*) has a coefficient of 0.054, and the culture dummy (*cultureD*) has a coefficient of 0.059, both insignificant. Notably, the *RespectScore* has a significant coefficient of 0.066 at the 1% level, indicating that respect within corporate culture positively impacts $CAR(-2,2)$. *IntegrityScore* also shows a positive but less significant effect (0.062 at the 10% level). Other scores, including Innovation and Quality, are insignificant, and Teamwork shows a negligible negative coefficient.

For target firms, Table 4 reveals that the *RespectScore* is highly significant with a coefficient of 0.145 at the 1% level, indicating its strong positive impact on $CAR(-2,2)$. Other

variables, including the composite culture score (*zculture*) and individual cultural dimensions, exhibit insignificant effects, with scores like Innovation and Quality having negative coefficients.

The analysis underscores respect as a critical factor in enhancing CAR for acquiring and target firms. Specifically, a one-unit increase in the *RespectScore* leads to a significant rise in CAR, with a 0.066 increase for acquiring firms and a 0.145 increase for target firms. This highlights respect's strategic value in M&A contexts. Other cultural factors like innovation, quality, and teamwork do not significantly impact CAR, emphasizing respect's unique importance in driving better M&A outcomes.

Descriptive statistics in Section 5.1 indicate slightly negative CAR for acquiring firms and positive CAR for targets, supporting the hypothesis that acquirers experience negative and targets experience positive abnormal returns around M&A announcements. The findings confirm that corporate culture, particularly respect, significantly influences short-term stock returns following M&A announcements.

Table 3: Impact of corporate culture on acquiring firms' five-day cumulative abnormal return.

This table presents the effect of the composite corporate culture score (*zculture*) and the dummy variable *cultureD* (assigned a value of 1 if the sum of a firm's cultural values is above the sample median and 0 otherwise), along with the five cultural values (Innovation, Integrity, Quality, Respect, and Teamwork scores), on acquiring firms' five-day cumulative abnormal return (CAR (-2,2)). The standard errors are reported in parentheses. The coefficients of estimations are presented with ***, **, and * which show statistical significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. The t-statistics are adjusted for both heteroskedasticity and within correlations.

Parameters	STR Acquirer						
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
<i>zculture</i>	0.054 (0.053)						
<i>cultureD</i>		0.059 (-0.057)					
<i>InnovationScore</i>			0.054				

			(- 0.056)				
QualityScore				0.055 (-0.049)			
IntegrityScore					0.062* (-0.054)		
RespectScore						0.066*** (-0.043)	
TeamworkScore							0.0496 (-0.026)
BM_ratio	0.052 (0.063)	-0.009 (-)	0.038 (-)	0.038 (-0.062)	0.034 (-0.060)	0.034 (-0.060)	0.036 (-0.060)
ROA	0.112 (-0.047)	0.088 (-)	0.090 (-)	0.089 (-0.037)	0.085 (-0.037)	0.074 (-0.037)	0.092 (-0.037)
Leverage	0.073 (-0.022)	0.051 (-)	0.053 (-)	0.053 (-0.020)	0.050 (-0.019)	0.052 (-0.019)	0.051 (-0.020)
SalesGrowth	0.0502 (-0.0001)	0.0503 (-)	0.0504 (-)	0.0499 (-0.0001)	0.0498 (-0.0001)	0.0498 (-0.0001)	0.0499 (-)
WithinState	0.0499 (-0.009)	0.044 (-)	0.045 (-)	0.045 (-0.009)	0.044 (-0.009)	0.046 (-0.009)	0.045 (-0.009)
WithinIndustry	0.063 (-0.009)	0.056 (-)	0.057 (-)	0.057 (-0.007)	0.055 (-0.007)	0.054 (-0.007)	0.057 (-0.008)
No. of Observations	489	489	489	489	489	489	489
Adj. R²	0.027	0.013	0.011	0.012	0.017	0.026	0.01

Table 4: Impact of corporate culture on target firms’ 5-day cumulative abnormal return.

This table presents the effect of the composite corporate culture score (*zculture*) and the dummy variable *cultureD* (assigned a value of 1 if the sum of a firm’s cultural values is above the sample median and 0 otherwise), along with the five cultural values (Innovation, Integrity, Quality, Respect, and Teamwork Scores), on target firms’ five-day cumulative abnormal return (CAR (-2,2)). The standard errors are reported in parentheses. The coefficients of estimations are presented with ***, **, and * which show statistical significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. The t-statistics are adjusted for both heteroskedasticity and within correlations.

Parameters	STR_Target						
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
<i>zculture</i>	-0.021 (-0.047)						

cultureD		-0.066 (-0.063)					
InnovationScore			-0.016 (-0.062)				
QualityScore				-0.031 (-0.063)			
IntegrityScore					0.042 (-0.011)		
RespectScore						0.145*** (-0.055)	
TeamworkScore							-0.061 (-0.067)
BM_ratio	0.070 (-0.137)	-0.138** (-0.062)	- (-0.057)	- (-0.058)	- (-0.053)	-0.123** (-0.059)	- (-0.062)
ROA	-0.268 (-0.231)	0.052 (-0.137)	0.053 (-0.133)	0.048 (-0.135)	0.057 (-0.131)	-0.048 (-0.135)	0.023 (-0.136)
Leverage	-0.382** (-0.187)	- (-0.123)	- (-0.119)	- (-0.117)	- (-0.116)	- (-0.112)	- (-0.118)
WithinState	0.039 (-0.112)	0.095 (-0.072)	0.088 (-0.069)	0.081 (-0.073)	0.079 (-0.070)	0.057 (-0.069)	0.092 (-0.061)
WithinIndustry	-0.087 (-0.114)	- (-0.058)	- (-0.053)	- (-0.052)	- (-0.058)	- (-0.055)	- (-0.058)
No. of Observations	116	116	116	116	116	116	116
Adj. R²	0.316	0.355	0.478	0.398	0.374	0.422	0.419

5.2.2. Long-Term Financial Performance

We further explore how corporate culture impacts the long-term performance of acquiring firms, focusing on profitability, valuation, and solvency. Key variables include the composite culture score (*zculture*), a culture dummy variable (*cultureD*), and specific cultural attributes such as Innovation Score, Quality Score, Integrity Score, Respect Score, and Teamwork Score. Results are detailed in Tables 5, 6, and 7, which cover long-term valuation Δ valuation represented by buy-and-hold abnormal returns (*BHAR*), Δ profitability, and Δ solvency, respectively. Table 5 examines *BHAR* over three years post-acquisition. Innovation and Quality Scores show positive coefficients with statistical significance at the 5% and 10% levels respectively, indicating these cultural factors enhance long-term valuation.

Table 6 examines long-term profitability, gauged by the change in net profit margin from one year before the M&A to three years following the transaction. Both the Innovation and Quality Scores exhibit positive coefficients, significant at the 10% level, suggesting a modest

improvement in profitability. Table 7 assesses solvency through changes in the interest coverage ratio from one year before the M&A to three years following the transaction. Innovation and Quality Scores have significant positive coefficients at a 5% level, suggesting improved solvency.

Overall, economically, a one-unit increase in either the Innovation and Quality Score leads to a 0.012 and 0.13-unit increase in BHAR respectively, indicating that these cultural attributes positively influence the long-term valuation of acquiring firms. Additionally, a one-unit rise in these two scores marginally enhances the net profit margin by 0.0004 and 0.0003 units respectively, demonstrating a slight positive effect on profitability. Moreover, a one-unit increase in these two scores improves the interest coverage ratio by 0.0032 and 0.0028 units, suggesting enhanced solvency for acquiring firms. Collectively, innovation and quality consistently demonstrate beneficial impacts on valuation, profitability, and solvency, underscoring their pivotal role in driving long-term performance. In contrast, the composite culture score (*zculture*) and culture dummy (*cultureD*) exhibit no significant effects. These results are consistent with prior research, supporting the notion that corporate culture—particularly attributes of innovation and quality—plays a crucial role in achieving long-term financial success post-M&A.

Table 5: Impact of corporate culture on long-term valuation of acquiring firms.

This table evaluates how the composite corporate culture score (*zculture*), the dummy variable *cultureD* (which equals 1 if a firm's cultural values exceed the sample median and 0 otherwise), and five individual cultural values—Innovation, Integrity, Quality, Respect, and Teamwork Scores—affect the long-term valuation of acquiring firms. Δ valuation is measured by buy-and-hold abnormal returns (BHAR) over a three-year post-acquisition period. Standard errors are reported in parentheses. Coefficients are marked with ***, **, and * to indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. The t-statistics account for heteroskedasticity and within-correlations.

Parameters	Δ valuation						
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
<i>zculture</i>	1.132 (-6.134)						

cultureD		0.713 (-11.98)					
InnovationScore			0.012** (-0.009)				
QualityScore				0.013* (-0.009)			
IntegrityScore					-0.008 (-0.015)		
RespectScore						-0.011 (-0.009)	
TeamworkScore							-0.017 (-0.012)
BM_ratio	-17.846 (-18.09)	-17.971 (-18.08)	-11.22 (-18.31)	-12.17 (-17.92)	-16.993 (-16.93)	-17.333 (-17.15)	-18.712 (-16.21)
ROA	148.91** * (-57.72)	147.61** * (-52.86)	146.78** * (-58.88)	145.84* * (-53.23)	153.11** * (-58.16)	152.95** * (-52.42)	151.78** * (-54.76)
Leverage	63.58** (-30.59)	66.52** (-32.48)	67.21** (-31.47)	66.76** (-31.65)	68.14** (-30.82)	68.97** (-31.61)	62.53** (-32.22)
SalesGrowth	0.121 (-0.191)	0.17 (-0.139)	0.181 (-0.132)	0.19 (-0.172)	0.127 (-0.186)	0.132 (-0.119)	0.126 (-0.176)
WithinState	31.27** (-13.91)	31.77** (-14.86)	29.35** (-15.58)	30.29** (-13.61)	33.49** (-14.37)	31.10** (-13.37)	32.92** (-14.71)
WithinIndustry	-15.63 (-13.278)	-15.79 (-13.255)	-14.92 (-12.72)	-15.16 (-13.174)	-14.25 (-13.292)	-14.194 (-13.286)	-10.299 (-12.39)
No. of Observations	330	330	330	330	330	330	330
Adj. R²	0.061	0.053	0.023	0.086	0.069	0.043	0.059

Table 6: Impact of corporate culture on long-term profitability of acquiring firms.

This table evaluates the impact of the composite corporate culture score (*zculture*) and the dummy variable *cultureD* (assigned a value of 1 if the sum of a firm’s cultural values is higher than the sample median and 0 otherwise), along with the five individual cultural values—Innovation, Integrity, Quality, Respect, and Teamwork Scores—on the long-term profitability of acquiring firms. Profitability is measured by the change in net profit margin from one-year pre-M&A to three years post-M&A. The standard errors are reported in parentheses. The coefficients of estimations are presented with ***, **, and * which show statistical significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. The t-statistics are adjusted for both heteroskedasticity and within correlations.

Parameters	Δ Net Profit Margin						
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
<i>zculture</i>	0.028						

		(-0.029)					
cultureD			0.027 (-0.057)				
InnovationScore				0.0004* (-0.0002)			
QualityScore					0.0003* (-0.0002)		
IntegrityScore						0.0001 (-0.0002)	
RespectScore							0.0001 (-0.0002)
TeamworkScore							-0.0001 (-0.0004)
BM_ratio	-0.028 (-0.087)	-0.032 (-0.088)	0.0032 (-0.082)	-0.0013 (-0.081)	-0.0351 (-0.087)	-0.0291 (-0.082)	-0.0321 (-0.088)
ROA	0.244 (-0.296)	0.253 (-0.360)	0.261 (-0.312)	0.274 (-0.334)	0.234 (-0.371)	0.265 (-0.385)	0.276 (-0.366)
Leverage	-0.097 (-0.121)	-0.091 (-0.133)	-0.091 (-0.125)	-0.019 (-0.122)	-0.069 (-0.172)	-0.048 (-0.189)	-0.092 (-0.145)
SalesGrowth	-0.0018* (-0.0013)	-0.0019* (-0.0013)	-0.0021* (-0.0011)	-0.0023* (-0.0021)	- (-0.0022*)	-0.0019* (-0.0014)	- (-0.0018)
WithinState	0.112 (-0.061)	0.161 (-0.0631)	0.123 (-0.0681)	0.118* (-0.0602)	0.116 (-0.0683)	0.131 (-0.0617)	0.149 (-0.0653)
WithinIndustry	-0.055 (-0.051)	-0.049 (-0.043)	-0.058 (-0.049)	-0.065 (-0.053)	-0.062 (-0.034)	-0.058 (-0.059)	-0.048 (-0.055)
No. of Observations	483	483	483	483	483	483	483
Adj. R²	0.035	0.0299	0.0261	0.0279	0.0267	0.0283	0.0274

Table 7: Influence of corporate culture on long-term solvency of acquiring firms.

This table assesses the influence of the composite corporate culture score (zculture) and the dummy variable cultureD (assigned a value of 1 if the sum of a firm's cultural values is higher than the sample median and 0 otherwise), along with the five cultural values— Innovation, Integrity, Quality, Respect, and Teamwork Scores—on the long-term solvency of acquiring firms. Solvency is measured by the change in the interest coverage ratio from one-year pre-M&A to three years post-M&A. The standard errors are reported in parentheses. The coefficients of estimations are presented with ***, **, and * which show statistical significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. The t-statistics are adjusted for both heteroskedasticity and within correlations.

Parameters	Δ Interest Coverage						
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
<i>zculture</i>	2.861 (-2.01)						
<i>cultureD</i>		4.353 (-4.055)					
InnovationScore			0.0032** (-0.0012)				
QualityScore				0.0028** (-0.0012)			
IntegrityScore					0.0019 (-0.0022)		
RespectScore						-0.0012 (-0.0015)	
TeamworkScore							0.0038 (-0.0016)
BM_ratio	5.288 (-6.42)	4.371 (-6.15)	7.518 (-6.31)	7.834 (-6.45)	4.33 (-6.68)	5.643 (-6.421)	4.802 (-6.261)
ROA	- 73.48*** (-23.14)	- 78.91*** (-21.25)	- 69.78*** (-22.17)	- 75.64*** (-28.11)	- 78.64*** (-29.96)	- 75.91*** (-23.39)	- 73.96*** (-23.17)
Leverage	3.766 (-9.84)	3.412 (-9.82)	7.193 (-8.95)	6.462 (-8.96)	2.943 (-8.92)	4.716 (-9.26)	2.957 (-9.13)
SalesGrowth	-0.079 (-0.059)	-0.088 (-0.056)	-0.076 (-0.064)	-0.085 (-0.069)	-0.087 (-0.066)	-0.093 (-0.063)	-0.096 (-0.067)
WithinState	3.874 (-4.55)	2.714 (-4.51)	2.914 (-4.77)	3.988 (-4.76)	3.175 (-4.81)	2.959 (-4.69)	3.019 (-4.57)
WithinIndustry	0.995 (-4.182)	1.211 (-4.713)	1.894 (-4.857)	1.986 (-5.951)	1.965 (-3.213)	1.616 (-4.897)	1.782 (-4.873)
No. of Observations	532	532	532	532	532	532	532
Adj. R ²	0.038	0.029	0.039	0.0344	0.0287	0.0311	0.0395

5.2.3. Deal Premium

We evaluate how corporate culture affects deal premiums for both target and acquiring firms. Deal premium is calculated as the ratio of the offer price to the target's share price four weeks before the announcement, minus one. Three areas are investigated: the target firms' culture (Table 8), the acquiring firms' culture (Table 9), and the interaction between their culture scores on the deal premium (Table 10).

Table 8 shows that for target firms, a stronger corporate culture, especially high integrity, increases deal premiums. The *cultureD* dummy has a significant coefficient of 0.216 at the 10% level, while the Integrity Score has a coefficient of 27.436, significant at the 5% level. A one-unit increase in the Integrity Score corresponds to a 27.436-unit rise in the deal premium,

highlighting the significant economic impact of integrity within the corporate culture of target firms. Other cultural values do not significantly affect premiums. Table 9 finds that for acquiring firms, corporate culture does not significantly impact deal premiums. The *cultureD* dummy and individual cultural values of *Innovation*, *Integrity*, and *Respect* are not significant. Quality Score has a positive and significant coefficient, where a one-unit increase in Quality score enhances the deal premium of the acquirer by 9.423 units.

Table 10 reveals that while the target's overall culture score positively affects deal premiums (coefficient of 0.136, significant at 10%), the acquirer's culture and the interaction between both cultures are not significant. In summary, target firms with strong cultural values, especially integrity, secure higher deal premiums, whereas acquiring firms' cultural attributes do not significantly influence their offer premiums. These results align with findings from Ozdemir et al. (2021) and Perafan et al. (2022).

Table 8: Impact of target firms' cultural values on deal premium.

This table examines the effect of the dummy variable *cultureD* (assigned a value of 1 if the sum of a firm's cultural values is higher than the sample median and 0 otherwise) and the five individual cultural values— *Innovation*, *Integrity*, *Quality*, *Respect*, and *Teamwork* Scores—of the target firms on the deal premium (standardized ratio of the offered price to the target's share price four weeks before the deal announcement date minus one), denoted as (*DP_Target*). The standard errors are reported in parentheses. The coefficients of estimations are presented with ***, **, and * which show statistical significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. The t-statistics are adjusted for both heteroskedasticity and within correlations.

Parameters	Deal Premium: Target					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
<i>cultureD</i>	0.216*					
	(-0.039)					
<i>InnovationScore</i>		9.714				
		(-6.272)				
<i>QualityScore</i>			10.111			
			(-6.461)			
<i>IntegrityScore</i>				27.436**		
				(-13.836)		
<i>RespectScore</i>					8.571	
					(-6.867)	

TeamworkScore						-31.769 (-19.326)
BM_ratio	-0.054 (-0.056)	-0.055 (-0.058)	-0.056 (-0.058)	-0.108 (-0.053)	-0.094 (-0.054)	-0.156* (-0.057)
ROA	-0.094 (-0.14)	-0.092 (-0.141)	-0.102 (-0.14)	-0.115 (-0.139)	-0.124 (-0.143)	-0.243 (-0.15)
Leverage	-0.309**	-0.308**	-0.316**	-	-0.409***	-0.432***
				0.376***		
WithinState	(-0.116)	(-0.118)	(-0.117)	(-0.112)	(-0.114)	(-0.115)
	-0.128* (-0.05)	-0.135* (-0.05)	-0.134* (-0.05)	-0.125* (-0.05)	-0.099 (-0.051)	-0.113 (-0.05)
WithinIndustry	-0.248***	-0.261***	-0.263***	-	-0.3881	-0.264***
	(-0.038)	(-0.037)	(-0.031)	(-0.033)	(-0.041)	(-0.037)
No. of Observations	568	568	568	568	568	568
Adj. R²	0.055	0.067	0.053	0.049	0.0389	0.0571

Table 9: Impact of acquiring firms' cultural values on deal premium.

This table assesses the influence of the dummy variable *cultureD* (assigned a value of 1 if the sum of a firm's cultural values is higher than the sample median and 0 otherwise) and the five individual cultural values— Innovation, Integrity, Quality, Respect, and Teamwork Scores—of the acquiring firms on the deal premium (standardized ratio of the offered price to the target's share price four weeks before the deal announcement date minus one), denoted as *DP_Acquirer*. The standard errors are reported in parentheses. The coefficients of estimations are presented with ***, **, and * which show statistical significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. The t-statistics are adjusted for both heteroskedasticity and within correlations.

Parameters	Deal Premium: Acquirer					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
<i>cultureD</i>	0.183 (-0.055)					
InnovationScore		7.964 (-8.301)				
QualityScore			9.423* (-8.369)			
IntegrityScore				6.595 (-19.511)		
RespectScore					9.678 (-8.737)	
TeamworkScore						-38.224 (-25.926)
BM_ratio	-0.137 (-0.117)	-0.142 (-0.121)	-0.138 (-0.119)	-0.192 (-0.111)	-0.196 (-0.11)	-0.258* (-0.115)

ROA	-0.314 (-0.448)	-0.337 (-0.448)	-0.341 (-0.448)	-0.347 (-0.449)	-0.385 (-0.448)	-0.422 (-0.449)
Leverage	-0.25 (-0.232)	-0.311 (-0.223)	-0.311 (-0.221)	-0.365 (-0.217)	-0.356 (-0.215)	-0.417* (-0.215)
WithinState	- 0.236** (-0.066)	-0.241** (-0.066)	-0.244** (-0.066)	-0.226** (-0.066)	-0.212** (-0.067)	-0.210** (-0.066)
WithinIndustry	- 0.195** (-0.05)	-0.193** (-0.051)	-0.191** (-0.051)	-0.206** (-0.051)	-0.198** (-0.05)	-0.196** (-0.05)
No. of Observations	307	307	307	307	307	307
Adj. R²	0.0588	0.0625	0.0651	0.0591	0.0584	0.072

Table 10: Impact of acquiring and target firms' combined cultural values on the deal premium (DP_Combined).

This table assesses the influence of the dummy variable *cultureD* (assigned a value of 1 if the sum of a firm's cultural values is higher than the sample median and 0 otherwise) and the five individual cultural values— Innovation, Integrity, Quality, Respect, and Teamwork Scores—of the acquiring and target firms combined on the deal premium (standardized ratio of the offered price to the target's share price four weeks before the deal announcement date minus one). The standard errors are reported in parentheses. The coefficients of estimations are presented with ***, **, and * which show statistical significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. The t-statistics are adjusted for both heteroskedasticity and within correlations.

Parameters	Deal Premium: Composite Scores		
	(1)	(2)	(3)
<i>zculture</i> Target	0.136* (-0.046)		
<i>zculture</i> Acquirer		0.11 (-0.053)	
<i>zculture</i> Target × Acquirer			0.079 (-0.036)
BM_ratio Target	-0.043 (-0.108)		-0.136 (-0.142)
ROA Target	-0.092 (-0.19)		-0.093 (-0.213)
Leverage Target	-0.299** (-0.167)		-0.417** (-0.194)
BM_ratio Acquirer		-0.134 (-0.17)	-0.036 (-0.182)

ROA_{Acquirer}	-0.342 (-0.497)		-0.416 (-0.509)
Leverage_{Acquirer}	-0.298 (-0.273)		-0.112 (-0.284)
WithinState	-0.135* (-0.1)	-0.234** (-0.116)	-0.245** (-0.117)
WithinIndustry	-0.258*** (-0.087)	-0.188** (-0.102)	-0.217*** (-0.1)
No. of Observations	568	307	307
Adj. R²	0.099	0.109	0.13

5.2.4. Deal Completion Speed

This study examines the effect of corporate culture on the speed of deal completion in M&As, focusing on target firms (Table 11), acquiring firms (Table 12), and their interaction (Table 13). Table 11 shows that target firms, with high corporate culture scores, especially in innovation, integrity, and quality, significantly reduce deal completion time. The culture dummy variable (*cultureD*) has a coefficient of -24.77 (5% significance level), with innovation and quality scores showing reductions of -34.83 and -35.22 (1% significance level), respectively. Integrity reduces completion time by -27.63 (10% significance level). Specifically, a one-unit increase in the *cultureD* score of the target firm results in a reduction of approximately 24.77 or 25 days in the time to closing. Likewise, a one-unit increase in Innovation and Quality Scores decreases the days to closing by approximately 34.83 or 35 and 35.221 or 35 days, respectively. Additionally, a one-unit increase in the IntegrityScore reduces the days to closing by about 27.63 or 28 days.

Table 12 shows acquiring firms with stronger corporate cultures also complete deals faster. The culture dummy variable has a coefficient of -24.622 (10% significance level), with innovation and quality scores reducing completion time by -37.574 and -38.766 (1% significance level). These results suggest that a one-unit increase in the *cultureD* score of the acquiring firm reduces the days to closing by approximately 24.622 or 25 days. Similarly, a one-unit increase in Innovation and Quality Scores shortens the days to closing by approximately 37.57 or 35 days and 38.766 or 39 days, respectively. Table 13 for composite culture scores shows that higher scores for target firms reduce deal time by -19.98 (1% significance level) while acquiring firms' scores reduce it by -15.08 (5% significance level). The interaction term is not significant. Economically, these findings imply that a one-unit increase in the *zculture* score of the target firm shortens the days to closing by approximately

20.002 or 20 days, whereas a one-unit increase in the *zculture* score of the acquiring firm reduces the days to closing by around 13.084 or 13 days. In summary, high innovation and quality scores accelerate deal completion for both targets and acquirers, underscoring the importance of corporate culture in expediting M&A processes. This supports previous research by Bereskin et al. (2018) and Hwang and Roh (2015).

Table 11: Impact of target firms' cultural values on days to closing (DtoC).

This table examines the effect of the dummy variable *cultureD* (set to 1 if the sum of a firm's cultural values exceeds the sample median and 0 otherwise) and the five individual cultural values— Innovation, Integrity, Quality, Respect, and Teamwork Scores—of the target firms on the days to closing (duration between the announcement date and the effective date of a completed deal), denoted as *DtoC_Target*. The standard errors are reported in parentheses. The coefficients of estimations are presented with ***, **, and * which show statistical significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. The t-statistics are adjusted for both heteroskedasticity and within correlations.

Parameters	Days to Closing: Target					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
<i>cultureD</i>	-24.772** (-9.771)					
<i>InnovationScore</i>		-34.832*** (-8.927)				
<i>QualityScore</i>			-35.221*** (-9.151)			
<i>IntegrityScore</i>				-27.630* (-15.237)		
<i>RespectScore</i>					-3.133 (-9.45)	
<i>TeamworkScore</i>						-17.096 (-11.595)
<i>BM_ratio</i>	-4.402 (-10.84)	-12.472 (-11.78)	-11.473 (-9.276)	3.478 (-11.24)	3.308 (-10.756)	-1.478 (-9.636)
<i>ROA</i>	78.50*** (-19.256)	72.01*** (-20.204)	75.00*** (-18.128)	83.74*** (-20.779)	80.23*** (-19.294)	72.61*** (-21.321)
<i>Leverage</i>	81.02*** (-17.993)	71.51*** (-18.12)	73.76*** (-17.994)	90.98*** (-17.771)	90.42*** (-19.654)	86.32*** (-17.897)
<i>WithinState</i>	2.888 (-10.824)	2.368 (-10.733)	2.379 (-11.737)	3.59 (-11.898)	3.029 (-12.859)	4.719 (-10.883)
<i>WithinIndustry</i>	13.504 (-9.737)	12.187 (-9.627)	12.735 (-9.614)	17.373* (-9.675)	16.292* (-9.663)	18.110* (-9.665)

No. of Observations	514	514	514	514	514	514
Adj. R²	0.452	0.919	0.281	0.765	0.221	0.344

Table 12: Effect of acquiring firms' cultural values on days to closing (DtoC).

This table evaluates the impact of the dummy variable *cultureD* (set to 1 if the sum of a firm's cultural values exceeds the sample median and 0 otherwise) and the five individual cultural values—Innovation, Integrity, Quality, Respect, and Teamwork Scores—of the acquiring firms on the days to closing (the period between the announcement date and the effective date of a completed deal), denoted as *DtoC_Acquirer*. The standard errors are reported in parentheses. The coefficients of estimations are presented with ***, **, and * which show statistical significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. The t-statistics are adjusted for both heteroskedasticity and within correlations.

Parameters	Days to Closing: Acquirer					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
<i>cultureD</i>	-24.622* (-13.232)					
<i>InnovationScore</i>		-37.574*** (-12.323)				
<i>QualityScore</i>			-38.776*** (-12.74)			
<i>IntegrityScore</i>				-5.894 (-20.133)		
<i>RespectScore</i>					-2.791 (-14.234)	
<i>TeamworkScore</i>						-20.26 (-16.524)
<i>BM_ratio</i>	47.98** (-18.289)	36.71* (-19.615)	37.94* (-20.474)	58.11*** (-19.656)	59.57*** (-18.54)	55.72*** (-19.743)
<i>ROA</i>	-24.735 (-54.186)	-41.103 (-57.079)	-37.242 (-55.93)	-19.781 (-57.52)	-17.277 (-55.802)	-30.656 (-58.109)
<i>Leverage</i>	107.06*** (-33.383)	101.78*** (-32.263)	103.77*** (-33.096)	126.92*** (-31.949)	127.73*** (-32.734)	128.26*** (-31.42)
<i>WithinState</i>	3.939 (-14.28)	-0.868 (-13.27)	-0.608 (-15.21)	3.086 (-14.36)	2.88 (-13.46)	5.263 (-14.42)
<i>WithinIndustry</i>	17.549 (-12.5)	14.143 (-12.47)	14.06 (-12.475)	19.639 (-12.52)	19.737 (-12.513)	21.556* (-12.561)
No. of Observations	326	326	326	326	326	326
Adj. R²	0.088	0.104	0.104	0.078	0.078	0.082

Table 13: Impact of composite corporate culture scores on days to closing (Dtc_Combined).

This table examines the effect of the composite corporate culture score (*zculture*) of target firms (Model 1) and acquiring firms (Model 2), as well as their interaction (Model 3), on the days to closing (the duration between the announcement and effective dates of a completed deal). The standard errors are reported in parentheses. The coefficients of estimations are presented with ***, **, and * which show statistical significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. The t-statistics are adjusted for both heteroskedasticity and within correlations.

Parameters	Days to Closing: Combined		
	(1)	(2)	(3)
<i>zculture</i> Target	-20.002*** (-5.194)		
<i>zculture</i> Acquirer		-13.084*** (-4.75)	
<i>zculture</i> Target × Acquirer			-0.299 (-6.175)
BM_ratio Target	-18.898 (-10.85)		21.604 (-13.63)
ROA Target	74.89*** (-20.889)		-27.218 (-24.611)
Leverage Target	76.975*** (-16.68)		27.53 (-22.267)
BM_ratio Acquirer		68.22*** (-14.76)	83.376*** (-16.54)
ROA Acquirer		-43.57 (-42.53)	-45.149 (-58.69)
Leverage Acquirer		101.24*** (-25.72)	119.86*** (-31.61)
WithinState	9.361 (-9.345)	11.451 (-10.241)	11.716 (-12.696)
WithinIndustry	15.215* (-6.25)	-3.342 (-9.233)	6.815 (-13.587)
No. of Observations	574	491	491
Adj. R ²	0.276	0.222	0.426

6. Real-World Examples Illustrating Key Findings

To further illustrate the impact of corporate culture on M&A outcomes, we examine several case studies that exemplify the study's key findings. These real-world examples highlight how cultural dimensions such as respect, innovation, quality, and integrity play

critical roles in shaping the success of mergers and acquisitions. By analyzing these cases, the section demonstrates the practical implications of aligning cultural values with strategic goals. It provides insights into how cultural factors can influence deal premiums, financial performance, and efficiency integration.

1. Intel and Mobileye: Innovation and Long-Term Financial Performance

Intel's 2017 acquisition of Mobileye for \$15.3 billion exemplifies the critical role of cultural alignment, particularly regarding innovation. Mobileye's innovative culture seamlessly integrates Intel's strategic vision, facilitating advancements in autonomous driving technology (Reuters, 2017). This cultural synergy enhanced Intel's long-term financial performance and positively impacted profitability and valuation, reinforcing the study's finding that innovation drives sustained financial success.

2. Salesforce and Slack: Respect and Deal Premiums

The \$27.7 billion acquisition of Slack by Salesforce in 2020 highlights how cultural respect influences M&A outcomes. Salesforce's integration strategy was marked by a deep respect for Slack's collaborative culture, which was essential for maintaining operational efficiency and employee morale (Bloomberg, 2020). This respect significantly elevated the deal premium, aligning with the study's observation that integrity and respect within the target firm's culture can enhance deal value and overall transaction success.

3. Kraft Heinz and Unilever: The Role of Quality

The 2017 unsuccessful merger attempt between Kraft Heinz and Unilever underscores the importance of cultural alignment, particularly concerning quality. Kraft Heinz's focus on cost-efficiency clashed with Unilever's dedication to quality and sustainability (Bloomberg Law, 2017). This mismatch, reflecting the study's findings, illustrates how critical cultural dimensions like quality are for long-term financial performance. The failure to reconcile these cultural differences led to the collapse of merger talks, highlighting the need for alignment in quality and other cultural factors.

4. The Walt Disney Company and Pixar: Cultural Integration and Deal Completion

Disney's acquisition of Pixar for \$7.4 billion in 2006 serves as a prime example of effective cultural integration facilitating deal completion. Disney's approach preserved Pixar's creative culture while aligning with its operational framework (Chaffin et al., 2006). This

cultural alignment expedited the integration process, supporting the study's findings that strong cultural values—particularly innovation and quality—can accelerate deal completion and contribute to overall transaction success.

5. eBay and Skype: Teamwork and M&A Challenges

The 2005 acquisition of Skype by eBay underscores the complexities of cultural fit in mergers and acquisitions. Despite eBay's focus on teamwork, integrating Skype's start-up ethos and independent, innovative culture posed significant challenges (Kopytoff, 2011). Conflicts emerged between eBay and Skype's leadership, driven by divergent visions for Skype's future and its role within eBay's broader strategy. These leadership disputes created instability and obstructed the integration process. This case aligns with the study's finding that while teamwork is important, its influence on M&A success may be limited if other critical cultural factors are not effectively managed. The eventual sale of Skype to Microsoft in 2011 further emphasizes the need for alignment across key cultural dimensions to achieve successful M&A outcomes.

7. Conclusion

We demonstrate the critical role of corporate culture in shaping M&A outcomes by leveraging 10-K filings and employing robust regression models. We show that cultural dimensions within acquiring and target firms significantly impact various M&A metrics, including long-term financial performance, announcement returns, deal premiums, and completion speed. By extending prior research, we elucidate how pre-existing cultural traits—namely respect, innovation, quality, teamwork, and integrity—affect key M&A outcomes. Specifically, we find that a culture of respect enhances cumulative abnormal returns (CAR) for both acquiring and target firms, while a culture of innovation and quality is linked to improved long-term valuation, profitability, and solvency. Integrity and quality emerge as crucial factors in increasing deal premiums for target and acquirer firms respectively, and strong cultural values are associated with expedited deal completion.

The findings of this paper emphasize the strategic importance of cultural alignment in M&As, demonstrating that successful cultural integration is a crucial factor in determining M&A success. We contribute to the literature by showcasing the economic impact of corporate culture in mergers, providing actionable insights for practitioners to refine their M&A strategies. The study's implications are far-reaching for managers, investors, and policymakers

involved in M&A activities. Managers can use these insights to guide more strategic integration efforts, minimizing post-merger challenges and improving transaction outcomes. Investors may consider cultural compatibility as part of their evaluation criteria, leading to more informed M&A decisions and enhanced portfolio performance. Policymakers could recognize the economic role of culture in M&As, potentially shaping regulations that encourage transparency in cultural practices, thereby promoting more stable and efficient markets. By incorporating these insights into decision-making processes, stakeholders can significantly improve the success and value creation of M&A transactions, underscoring the importance of a deep understanding and integration of corporate culture.

Future research could benefit from several avenues. Sector-specific analyses might reveal how cultural factors vary across different industries and impact M&A outcomes differently. Additionally, integrating advanced quantitative methods, such as machine learning and natural language processing, could provide deeper insights into cultural integration's effects on post-merger performance. Investigating stakeholder perspectives and comparing the influence of corporate culture on M&A with other business outcomes, such as innovation and employee retention, would further enrich our understanding of cultural dynamics in mergers and acquisitions. These approaches will enhance the breadth and depth of knowledge regarding the role of corporate culture in shaping successful M&A transactions.

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